

Yu.Podrez

Sumy State Pedagogical University by Makarenko
uliya.podriez@gmail.com

**RESEARCH OF THE ROLE OF BUSINESS MANAGEMENT OF UKRAINIAN DI-
ASPORY IN MODERNIZATION OF THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE IN THE SECOND HALF
OF THE XIXth - BEGINNING OF XX CENTURIES. IN THE HISTORY PRE - Soviet
HISTORIOGRAPHY**

В статті проведено огляд дорадянської історіографії 1871 – 1917 рр., де розглядається становлення малого промислового підприємництва серед українського етнічного населення Російської імперії. Наведено перші публікації по даній проблемі, в яких міститься інформація щодо пошуку найбільш раціональних шляхів подальшого розвитку малого промислового підприємництва, перспективам ринкової трансформації традиційних кустарних промислів.

Автор зазначає, що більшість із вказаних у статті робіт носили публіцистичний характер і були ще далекими від вимог, що ставляться до історичних досліджень.

Аналізуючи роботи дослідників з даної проблеми, зазначається, що переконлива більшість тодішніх економістів, земських діячів, публіцистів у своїх роботах намагаються довести здатність дрібнотоварного виробництва існувати тривалий час поруч з великими заводами і фабриками.

В статті зазначено, що після створення в грудні 1872 р. «Комісії з дослідження кустарної промисловості в Росії» починається етап наукової вивченості та дослідження

кустарної промисловості. Автором детально подається інформація про роботу даної Комісії та її заходи, щодо державного сприяння дрібному промисловому підприємництву.

Ключові слова: дослідження, історіографія, українська діаспора, кустарно-реміснича промисловість, мале промислове підприємництво.

В статтю произведено анализ историографии 1871 – 1917 гг., в которой рассматривается развитие малого примышленного производства среди этнического украинского населения Российской империи. В данной статье рассмотрено первые публикации по данной проблеме, в которых содержится информация касательно поиска рациональных возможностей дальнейшего развития малого примышленного производства, перспективы рыночной трансформации традиционных кустарных промыслов.

Автор акцентує увагу на тому, що більшість із указаних в статті робіт носили публіцистичний характер і були далекі від тих вимог, які ставить перед собою історична наука.

Аналізуючи роботи дослідників того часу, автор відзначає, що значительное большинство экономистов, земских деятелей, публицистов пытаются в своих трудах доказать возможность мелкого товарного производства существовать длительное время параллельно с большими заводами и фабриками.

Автор відзначає, що після створення Комісії по вопросу исследования кустарной промышленности в России (декабрь 1872 г.) начинается этап научного становления, а так же исследования кустарной промышленности. Информация, касательно деятельности данной Комиссии автором детально изучена и результаты предложены в данной статье.

Ключевые слова: исследования, историография, украинская диаспора, кустарно-ремесленная промышленность, малое производство.

The article reviews the pre-Soviet historiography of 1871 - 1917, where the formation of small industrial enterprise among the Ukrainian ethnic population of the Russian Empire is considered. The first publications on this issue are presented, which contain information on finding the most rational ways for the further development of small industrial enterprises, and the prospects for the market transformation of traditional handicrafts.

The author notes that most of the articles mentioned in the article were journalistic and were still far from the requirements of historical research.

Analyzing the work of researchers on this problem, it is noted that the convincing majority of the then economists, Zemstvo figures, publicists in their work try to prove the ability of small-scale production to exist for a long time, along with large factories and factories.

The article states that after the creation in December, 1872, "Commission for the Study of Handicraft Industry in Russia" begins the stage of scientific study and research of the handicraft industry. The author details in detail the work of this Commission and its measures on state assistance to small-scale industrial entrepreneurship.

Key words: research, historiography, Ukrainian diaspora, handicrafts and crafts, small industrial entrepreneurship.

In today's conditions for the national historical science, the study of the development of the Ukrainian diaspora in the socio-economic space of remains very relevant and represents considerable scientific and practical interest. Without studying it, it is impossible to understand in all its completeness, variety and complexity the general history of the Ukrainian diaspora.

In the pre-Soviet period, the development of scientific thought regarding the socio-economic development of regions of

compact and dispersed habitation of Ukrainians, which during the second half of the XIX - early XX centuries were located within the administrative boundaries of the Russian provinces and regions, it should be noted that, according to the number of published works and the depth of coverage, this topic was not often in the sight of historians, economists, ethnographers, culturologists, zemstvo figures and publicists. But precisely at this time there were the first publications in which, on the general background of the development of the

handicraft industry of the Russian Empire, attempts were made to analyze the formation of small industrial enterprise among the Ukrainian ethnic population of Russia.

The purpose of the article is to review the pre-Soviet historiography of the second half of the XIX - early XX centuries. It is devoted to ethno-cultural aspects of the history of small industrial entrepreneurship and industrial-industrial cooperation on Ukrainian ethnic lands outside the Dnieper Ukraine.

The first serious scientific work, which compared the development of the handicraft industry in Russia and Western Europe, was written by economist O.K. Korsak and it was published in 1861. It based on statistical data collected by the General Staff and the Ministry of State Property, O.K. Korsak showed the place and role of the handicraft industry in the socio-economic life of the Russian Empire, assessing this form of industry as "a very significant form of production" [22, c.2]. In addition, the scale and forms of the development of handicrafts in various provinces and regions with similar processes in Western Europe have been successfully compared and an important conclusion is drawn about the existence of a common civilization road for the development of small industrial enterprises, including for the Ukrainian ethnic lands of Russia. However, Korsak shared the widespread misconception about his impossibility to overcome a number of negative moments inherent in handicraft production in the period he considered [22, p.306, 307].

The first publications outlined some issues of the participation of ethnic Ukrainians in the development of various handicraft and handicraft industries, the problems of the establishment and development of Ukrainian handicraft cells on Russian lands of the Russian Empire and, in particular, in many regions of the central provinces and regions of Russia, in Siberia, the Far East, the Kuban, Lower and Middle Volga, Eastern Slobozhanshchyna. Their appearance was closely linked with the practice and plans of the Russian government regarding the economic modernization of the country. It is these articles and articles that are devoted to the search for the most rational ways of fur-

ther development of small industrial enterprises, including among the ethnic Ukrainian population, the prospects for the market transformation of traditional handicrafts. Written on various occasions and on various topics of publications of this period were journalistic and were still far from the requirements relating to historical research. Only O.O. Meshchersky and K.M. Modzalevskii on the basis of official statistical data, Modzalevsky managed to show the place and discover the role of Ukrainian small-scale industrialists in the socio-economic life of many Russian provinces and regions. They highly appreciated the skill of Ukrainian folk craftsmen who lived outside the Dnieper Ukraine [25].

Thanks to the consolidated efforts of the Russian Technical Society, the Society for the Promotion of Russian Industry and Trade, the Free Economic Society, the South Russian Society of Agriculture, the Moscow Society of Agriculture in the pre-Soviet period, it was written a large number of scientific and popular scientific works devoted to the study of certain aspects of the development of small industrial enterprise among the Ukrainian ethnic population of Russia. Among them, the number and depth of the study of economists and Zemstvo figures of the Populist direction. Taking a lot of attention to socio-economic problems, they often quite idealized small-scale industrial entrepreneurship. Thus, one of the most famous ideologues of Populism V.P. Vorontsov in a number of his works convincingly argued, on the basis of the actual material, the ability of small-scale production to exist for a long time along with large factories and factories. He also called on the state and society to comprehensively promote the widespread development of small industrial enterprises of the Ukrainian population of Russia [3].

Authors such as E.M. Andreev [1], K. Bucher [2], G. Wagner, P.O. Geselukus, V. Pavlovich, O. Bratchikov and many others also showed considerable interest in the study of handicrafts and crafts of the Ukrainian ethnic population of Russia. Describing artisanal crafts as "popular production", they managed to reveal many positive trends in their development, in particular the growth of the number of Ukrainian small-scale industrialists, the

creation in Ukrainian enclaves of Russia of conditions for the emergence of new productions, the expansion of their geography, the progressive improvement of technology and technology, etc. In the 90 years of the XIX century. At the All-Russian level, in the controversy with populist-minded authors on the question of the path and nature of the economic development of post-reform Russia, the ideologists of the great industrial bourgeoisie and representatives of Marxist trends actively joined. In the books and articles P.B. Struve [31], M.I. Tugan-Baranovsky [36] and others criticized the populist idealistic views on the place and role of handicrafts in the national economy of the Russian Empire.

The most decisive step in the formulation and scientific development of the development problem in handicraft industry in Russia, including the Ukrainian ethnic industrial enterprise, is in the second half of the 1870s - the first half of the 1880s and is associated with the activities of the Commission for the Study of Handicraft Industry in Russia ". It was created by the Russian government in December 1872 under the Council of Trade and Manufactures. The structure of the Artistic Commission includes representatives of the Ministries of Finance, Internal Affairs, State Property and various non-governmental organizations. The chairman of the commission was appointed Professor of Technology E.M. Andreyev is the author of a thorough research on the history of the handicraft industry. It was in the Handicraft Commission that gradually concentrated the entire work on the definition and development of measures to promote state small-scale industrial entrepreneurship [1, p. 7].

Having considered their plans and budget, the commission decided to organize research on the development of handicrafts in certain provinces and counties of the Russian Empire, allocating 16.8 thousand rubles to this. In many provinces, a network of correspondents of the commission was set up, in which the authoritative experts of their region acted, mainly from among the employees of the provincial administration and statistical committees, university professors, zemstvo leaders, nobles and landowners [34, p. 10]. So, in 1883 the correspondent of the commis-

sion G. Arsenyev completed the study of the handicraft industry of the Vologda province. Borisov explored the artisan industry of the Tula province., G.Kozachenko - the artisan industry of the Lyubovytzia province., G.Tillo - the artisan industry of the Kostroma province. [33, p. 274-277]. In 1884, the correspondent of the commission, Isaev reported on the completion of the study of the artisan industry of the Yaroslavl Gubernia., Gatsysky - investigated the artisan industry of the Nizhny Novgorod province., Monochin - the artisan industry of the Perm gubernia. Only in some provinces, for example, the Nizhny Novgorod and Yaroslavl Commission was forced to temporarily cease its work because of the opposition of local governors [32, p. 305, 328-329]. The Commission also made the first steps to provide various practical assistance to small-scale industrialists, which the Treasury allocated for 13277 rubles during 1877-1886 [35, p. 9].

In general, the research activity of the Artistic Commission allowed collecting rich information about the state of the handicraft industry, which was later concentrated in the library of the commission. The most important information collected by the correspondents of the commission was reflected in numerous articles and comments on official documents collected in the Commission's proceedings, which were published in separate issues from 1879 to 1887. Complementing each other, the correspondents of the commission showed quite a few aspects of the participation of ethnic Ukrainians in the development of small industrial entrepreneurship in certain Russian provinces and regions. In particular, they attempted to identify the peculiarities and forms of accelerated market transformation of Ukrainian handicraft cells in Siberia, the Far East, the Kuban, the Lower and Middle Volga, Eastern Slobozhanshchyna and other regions of Russia. They showed the local geography of handicrafts, gave a detailed description of a number of productions, commodity division of labor, the state of the raw material base and markets for handicraft products, and provided data on the activities of state authorities on the development of cottage industry. At the same time, the authors described far not all aspects of the develop-

ment of the handicraft industry in the Ukrainian ethnic lands, often using a different methodology. In addition, the works reflected the regularities and peculiarities of the participation of ethnic Ukrainians in the development of small-scale industrial entrepreneurship.

Among the authors, whose works were published in the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. In the multi-volume collection "Reports and Researches on the Handicraft Industry in Russia," handicraft techniques and other well-trained highly educated specialists who served in the central ministries and departments prevailed. Their immediate responsibilities included the collection and analysis of information on the artisanal industry of all regions of the Russian Empire, and therefore the article M.I. Shevlyagina V.V. Lozovsky, F.N. Korolev, P.T. Oleinikova, M.V. Ponomariov and other scholars were rich in actual material and generalization. For example, in articles by M.I. Shevlyagin some aspects of the participation of representatives of the Ukrainian diaspora of the Kursk and Nizhny Novgorod provinces in the development of leather crafts were shown [38]; in the articles of V.V. Lozovsky investigated the development of cartoons and artisan production in Ukrainian handicraft centers of the Kursk province [24]; in articles by F.N. Korolyov showed some aspects of the development of handicrafts and pottery in the Ukrainian enclaves of the Vyatka, Perm, Smolensk, Simbirsk and some other provinces of Russia [20; 21]; in Articles P.T. Oleinikov had a significant influence of ethnic Ukrainians on the development of pottery in the Smolensk, Penza and other Russian provinces [27]; in the articles MV Ponomariov attempted to analyze the influence of the Ukrainian ethno-cultural factor on the sectoral and regional features of the development of small industrial entrepreneurship in the Kursk province [29].

Of great interest in the study of the historiography of our scientific problem are also V.V. Biryukovich, B. Veselovsky, O.O. Karelina, I.P. Gliwice, M.V. Dovnar-Zapolsky, M.F. Danielsson, F.S. Golitsyn, O.O. Isaeva, O.S. Ermolova, O.O. Alova and others like that. Following on the general so-

cio-economic development of both individual regions and the Russian Empire as a whole, they have, in this context, determined the evolution of certain types of small industrial entrepreneurship of ethnic Ukrainians in Eastern Slobozhanshchyna, Kuban, Lower and Middle Volga, Siberia, the Far East and other regions. Not hiding their personal sympathies for folk crafts, they showed bright pages of the development of handicrafts and crafts, including the ethno-cultural aspects of this process in post-reform Russia. Yes, the materials are collected in the monograph M.M. Kozmin allows us to trace the processes of settlement of Siberia by Ukrainians and the creation of Ukrainian handicraft cells here [19]. Scientific works of S.O. According to the level of depth of analysis, the size of the source base, the range of issues covered, and the methodology of approaches, in our opinion, remain the best works on the history of small industrial entrepreneurship in the Eastern Slobozhanshchyna, written in pre-Soviet times [5-14].

At the beginning of the XX century there is mostly optimistic about the small industrial entrepreneurship of ethnic Ukrainians of Russian provinces and regions and many other authors. So, using a large statistical material, some ethno-cultural aspects of the development of handicrafts in Russia explored M.V. Ponomarev describing some areas of the handicraft industry, for example, he often used data on handicraft cells in the Ukrainian ethnic enclaves of Russia. Bringing his own classification of crafts, looking in detail at each of the identified groups [26]. And the well-known economist C. Buher, arguing that the handicraft industry "will last for a long time next to the factory," argued the historical progressiveness and perspective of the development of small industrial enterprises among the Ukrainian ethnic population of Russian provinces and regions [2, p. 17]. In the studies of Professor M.O. Kablukova was given the definition of the cottage industry as a small-scale production, also pointed out that in many Ukrainian handicrafts, depending on the nature of the needs of the local population, the preservation of aristocracy is necessary and inevitable. Special attention to M.O. Kablukov paid attention to the problems of devel-

opment of cooperation among small industrial entrepreneurs, including among representatives of the Ukrainian diaspora [17-18]. An attempt to determine the place and role of handicraft crafts and crafts of the Ukrainian ethnic population of n provinces and regions in the national economy of was made in the work of prof. V.F. Levitsky [23].

Significant contribution to the scientific development of the problem of distribution among the Ukrainian ethnic population of small-scale wood-processing industries has made its thorough monograph M.O. Filippov, who was a member of the Department of Rural Economy and Agricultural Statistics. However, the author limited himself mainly to the description of woodworking industries in certain regions of the compact residence of ethnic Ukrainians in the Russian provinces and regions, the identification of facts, events and figures without their proper ethno-cultural analysis [37]. Measures of the government, zemstvos and private individuals, aimed at preventing the pauperization of the aristocratic population of Russia, including small-scale industrialists from Ukrainian handicraft cells, were detailed in O.D. Postage, dedicated to the prospects of the development of the handicraft industry at the turn of the XIX - XX centuries [28]. Historians of the Russian national economy M.V. Dovnar-Zapolsky [4] and M.F. Denisyuk [15] considered separate ethnic and culturological aspects of handicrafts and crafts in the conditions of socio-economic modernization of Russia in the second half of the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries.

Among the researches devoted to the development of small industrial entrepreneurship among the Ukrainian population of the Eastern Slobozhanshchyna, the monograph M.O. Dobrotvorskiibecame the most successful among the works of the pre-Soviet period. Dobrotvorsky's "Crafts of the Kursk Province," in which the place and role of handicrafts and handicrafts of the Ukrainian ethnic population in the socio-economic develop-

ment of the Eastern Slobozhanshchyna were determined [16]. No less successful from the works of the pre-Soviet period was the monograph of O.O. Rybnikova and O.S. Orlova "Handicraft and the sale of handicraft products", published in 1913 [30]. The research of these authors is essential for its specific part, which attempted to give a general statistical, economic and geographic review of small industrial enterprise of the Russian Empire, including to consider certain aspects of the participation of ethnic Ukrainians in the development of small-scale industry in Siberia, the Far East, the Kuban, Lower and Middle Volga, Eastern Slobozhanshchyna and other regions of Russia. His calculations of the number of Ukrainian handicrafts by provinces and counties O.O. Rybnikov and O.S. Orlova were among the first to be built entirely on materials of Zemstvo statistics. Thus, M.O. Dobrotvorsky, O.O. Rybnikov and O.S. Orlov not only significantly advanced the study of ethnic aspects of the history of handicraft industry in Russia, but also one of the first began to seriously develop the necessary methodological approaches and principles for this. That they made an attempt to overcome the local fragmentation of Zemstvo statistical materials by a mathematical method.

Conclusions In general, the pre-Soviet period of historiography of our problem was characterized by the use of fragmentary data on the development of small industrial entrepreneurship among the Ukrainian ethnic population and on the contribution of Ukrainian business community in the socio-economic development of certain regions of Russia, mostly based on questionnaires and personal surveys of authors of works. Doyadian historiography did not have time to systematize socio-economic history of the Ukrainian diaspora of Russia. However, during this period a considerable amount of actual material was accumulated, a number of key issues were addressed that addressed important aspects of the development of individual crafts and crafts in the Ukrainian ethnic lands of Russia.

REFERENCES

1. Andreev E.N. Handicrafts in Russia in the research of the Commission for the Study of Handicraft Industry in Russia

- / E.N. Andreev - SPb .: Type. V. Kirschbaum, 1885. - 96 p.
2. B. Buher K. The emergence of a national economy / K. Buher. - Spb .:

- Type. t-va "commonly. use ", 1912. - 313 pp.
3. Vorontsov V.P. Value of handicrafts, general conditions of their development and measures for their maintenance in Russia // VP Vorontsov - SPb .: Type. V. Kirschbaum, 1902. - 27 pp.
 4. Davnar-Zapolsky MV History of the Russian national economy / M.V. Dovernar-Zapolski. - K .: Type. Chokolov, 1911. - Vol.1. - 8, 366 pp.
 5. Davydova S.A. Lure fishing in Podolsk and Serpukhov districts of the Moscow province. Travel notes / Sofya Aleksandrovna Davydova // Proceedings of the Commission for the Study of Handicraft Industry in Russia. - SPb .: Type. V. Kirschbaum, 1880. - Izp. V. - S. 413-425.
 6. Davydova S.A. Lure Fishing in Russia / Sophia Alexandrovna Davydova. - St. Petersburg, 1902. - 163 p.
 7. Davydova S.A. Lure fishing in the Ryazan province. Travel notes / Sofya Aleksandrovna Davydova // Proceedings of the Commission for the Study of Russian Handicraft Industry. - SPb .: Type. V. Kirschbaum, 1881. - P. 116-190.
 8. Davydova S.A. Handicraft industry of Vladimir, Kursk, Poltava, Bessarabskaya and Voronezh provinces / Sofya Aleksandrovna Davydova // Reports and studies on the artisanal industry in Russia. - SPb .: Type. V. Kirschbaum, 1892. - Vol.1. - P. 72 - 144.
 9. Davydova S.A. Russian handicraft industry. Women's crafts / S.A. Davydova, E.N. Polotskaya, K.I. Berens, E.O. Svidersky - SPb .: Izd. Department of the SS and SS, 1913. - 440 p.
 10. Davydova S.A. Sketch of the lace industry of Russia / Sofya Aleksandrovna Davydova // Handicraft industry of Russia. Women's crafts. - SPb .: Izd. Department of the SS and SS, 1913. - P. 3-182.
 11. Davydova S.A. Essay on the production of beadwork in the Chernivtsi district of the Tula province of Russia / S.A. Davydov // Handicraft industry of Russia. Women's crafts. - SPb .: Izd. Department of the SS and SS, 1913. - P. 375-378.
 12. Davydova S.A. Sketch of Carpet Production in Russia / S.A. Davydov // Handicraft Industry of Russia. Women's crafts. - SPb .: Izd. Department of the SS and SS, 1913. - P. 279-343.
 13. Davydova S.A. An Essay on Pumice Craft in Russia / S.A. Davydov // Handicraft Industry of Russia. Women's crafts. - SPb .: Izd. Department of the SS and SS, 1913. - P. 252.
 14. Davydova S.A. Russian lace and Russian lace / S.A. Davydova. - SPb .: Type. V. Kirschbaum, 1892. - 59 p.
 15. Denisyuk NF Kustarnaia Russia / NF Denisyuk - Pg .: Sport and Speakers, 1918. - 166 pp.
 16. Dobrotvorsky N.A. Handicrafts of the Kursk province / N.A. Dobrotvorsky - Kursk: 1886. - 255 p.
 17. Kablukov N.A. Handicraft industry and its connection with cooperatives. - Moscow, 1915. - 179 pp.
 18. Kablukov N.A. About statistical research of handicraft industries in Russia / N.A. Kablukov // Proceedings of the Congresses of Persons in the Handicraft Industry in St. Petersburg. - SPb., 1910. - Ch.1-111. - P. 83.
 19. Kozmin N.N. Essays of the past and present Siberia / N.N. Kozmin - SPb .: Type. "Printed Labor", 1910. - 266 pp.
 20. Korolev FN Pottery in Vyatka, Perm and some other provinces / FN Korolev // Reports and studies on the artisan industry in Russia. T. 3. - SPb .: Type. V. Kirschbaum, 1895. - p. 79-90
 21. Korolev FN Potting in the Smolensk and Vyatka gubernias. and the production of agricultural implements and machines in the Simbirsk Bay. / Fn Korolev // Reports and researches on the Russian handicraft industry. T. 2. - SPb .: Type. V. Kirschbaum, 1894. - p. 88-95.
 22. Korsak AK On the forms of industry in general and about the importance of home production (handicraft and home industry) in Western Europe and

- Russia / AK Tartar fox. - M .: Type. Grachev and K °, 1861. - 310 c.
23. Levitsky V.F. On the Importance of Handicrafts in the National Economy / VF Levitsky - Poltava: Publishing the lips. zemstvos, 1909. - 69 p.
24. Lozovskoy V.V. Basketball and solid production in Kharkiv, Kursk, Ryazan and other provinces / VV Lozovskaja // Reports and studies on the artisanal industry in Russia. - SPb .: Type. V. Kirschbaum, 1900. - Vol. 6. - P. 343-367.
25. Meshchersky AA A collection of materials on the handicraft industry in Russia / AA Meshchersky, KN Modazalevsky - SPb .: Type. Panteleev, 1874. - 4, 9, 630 pp.
26. Review of government assistance to the handicraft industry. - SPb .: Type. V. Kirschbaum, 1913. - 125 p.
27. Olkhova L.V. Small Industry of the Urals at the Beginning of the 20th Century (1905-1913): Author's abstract. Dis ... Cand. yes Sciences: 07.00.02 / L.V. Alder - Sverdlovsk, 1964. - 26 p.
28. Pogubernnye results of the All-Russian agricultural land census of 1917 in 52 guberniyas and oblasts. - M .: 14th state. type., 1921. - bs
29. Ponomarev N.V. Handicrafts in Russia / N.V. Ponomarev - SPb .: Type. MM Gutzats, 1900. - 79 p.
30. Rybnikov AA Small Industry and Its Role in the Restoration of the National Economy / AA Rybnikov - M .: Type. T-va "Cooperative Publishing House", 1922. - 52 p.